

The Reform of the CAP and Development Trends of Rural Law¹

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Abstract

À l'occasion d'une conférence donnée à l'occasion du 30e anniversaire de la Société finlandaise de droit agricole, l'auteur aborde trois sujets : L'adhésion de la Finlande à l'UE en 1995 et son importance pour la politique agricole commune, les étapes importantes de son développement juridique et institutionnel et le modèle de mise en œuvre de la nouvelle PAC d'un point de vue juridique.

Der Autor behandelt anlässlich eines Vortrags des 30-Jahr-Jubiläums der finnischen Agrarrechtsgesellschaft drei Themenbereiche: Finnlands EU-Beitritt 1995 und seine Bedeutung für die Gemeinsame Agrarpolitik, bedeutende Marksteine deren rechtlicher und institutioneller Entwicklung sowie das "delivery model" der neuen GAP aus rechtlicher Sicht.

I have been asked to speak about the "CAP reform and development trends in rural law". When I thought about it I rapidly identified such a number of subjects that I could easily speak to you for several hours. As this is not a realistic proposition I have picked some issues and questions which I imagine might also interest you. So, I will first briefly recall Finland's accession to the European Economic Community and its implications for the CAP. Then I would like to discuss some important landmarks for the legal and institutional development of the CAP. Finally, I will comment on the ongoing reform process and discuss the new CAP delivery model proposed by the Commission from a legal perspective.

1.

When Finland joined the EEC in 1995 together with Sweden and Austria, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) became applicable to Finnish agriculture as of day one. By contrast, Spain and Portugal, after joining nine years earlier, still had had to undergo a lengthy and complex transition process. These two countries were in particular subject to a mechanism of monetary compensatory amounts aimed at smoothening the otherwise distortive effects arising in a system based on institutional prices and market measures.

That Finland, such as Sweden and Austria, escaped this regime was largely due to two important changes the EEC had implemented some years before:

- First, the MacSharry reform had moved the CAP away from a system of highly regulated market price and border protection to a market-oriented policy model based primarily on

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direct income support, in order to compensate farmers for income losses resulting from reduced market prices.²

- Second, at about the same time, the single European market without border controls on goods was completed, which would have prevented the application of monetary compensatory amounts at internal borders anyway.

The new CAP model not only allowed to gradually eliminate the various flaws of “the old CAP” such as production surpluses, excessive stocks and trade distorting export subsidies. It also created the conditions for integrating the CAP into the WTO trading system resulting from the Uruguay Round. With a view to the accession of Finland, Sweden and Austria, it thus paved the way for the immediate integration of the three countries into the internal market and the CAP. So, these three new Member States benefited from starting their membership under the conditions of a new forward-looking policy concept.³

Of course, this does not mean that the accession could have been arranged without transitional measures. As regards Finland there were mainly two important issues:

- First, the need to address the effects of reducing the much higher Finnish agricultural prices to price levels in the EEC.
- And second, Finland's request to take account of the specific geographical and climatic patterns of its agricultural sector and the resulting disadvantages.⁴

To this end, in addition to other arrangements e.g. concerning less favoured areas, two important, and one may even say emblematic, schemes were agreed:

- in Article 142 of the Act of Accession, a specific national support scheme for Nordic agriculture i.e. areas situated to the north of the 62nd parallel, which in 2018 was still worth approximately 320 million € and
- another scheme in Article 141 of the Act of Accession, authorising Finland to grant national aid to farmers in the South of the country. Although Article 141 is no longer operational, the same type of payments, albeit at much lower levels than in the beginning (roughly 23 million € in 2018), are now granted by virtue of Article 214a of the CMO Regulation⁵ under the heading "National payments for certain sectors in Finland".

Overall, it is fair to say that Finnish agriculture has managed since 1995 to find its place in the European context.⁶ On the one hand, it is faced with similar challenges as agriculture in other Member States such as structural change, agricultural income lagging behind general income levels, digitisation or problems in rural areas. However, coupled and decoupled payments, rural development support and national support, totalling in 2018 more than 1.7 billion € have helped to address the geographical

² Demarty, Mögele, Haniotis, 60 ans de politique agricole commune, RDE 2019, pp. 17, 25 et seq.

³ Mögele in Merli/Huster (ed.), Die Verträge zur EU-Osterweiterung, 2008, pp. 231, 236.

⁴ See Niemi, Twenty Years after – Welfare effects of the application of the CAP in Austria, Finland and Sweden, Proceedings of the 25th NJF Congress, Riga 2015, pp. 428 et seq.

⁵ Regulation (EU) 1308/2013.

⁶ See Tomsik, Rosochatecka, Competitiveness of the Finnish Agriculture after ten years in the EU, Agric. Econ. – Czech, 53, 2007 (10), pp. 448 et seq.; Niemi, Twenty Years after – Welfare effects of the application of the CAP in Austria, Finland and Sweden, Proceedings of the 25th NJF Congress, Riga 2015, pp. 428 et seq.; Niemi, Väre (eds.), Agriculture and food sector in Finland 2018, Natural resources and bioeconomy studies 35/2018.

and climatic specificities in the country. This of course also means that the share of public subsidies in agricultural factor income in Finland is above 50% which is higher than EU average but by far not the highest of all Member States.⁷

2.

In 2019 the CAP is obviously no longer the same as it was in 1995. In the 24 years that have elapsed since Finland's accession, the transition to a market-oriented policy was gradually completed namely in the contexts of Agenda 2000, the Fischler reform of 2003, the Health Check 2009 and finally the 2013 reform - the latter confirming the expiry of the last remnants of the pre-MacSharry-CAP, i.e. milk quotas and sugar quotas. Furthermore, the integration of European agriculture in the world market by a whole series of free trade agreements did certainly open up new opportunities.⁸ But it also led to greater price volatility and increasing competitive pressures. Further rounds of enlargements expanded the number of Member States from 15 to 28 and made the Union more heterogeneous than ever, also in respect of its agricultural sector. In parallel, and this is an important point to make especially with regard to the current MFF negotiations, the budget available for the CAP has basically been kept stable in real terms, despite the accession of many new Member States. Obviously, this had the effect of decreasing the value of CAP support per unit over the years.

3.

In parallel, the CAP's institutional and legal framework underwent a number of significant changes which have left their traces in the way the CAP operates and it is perceived by its actors and addressees. This is true even though the agricultural community may not always be sufficiently aware of these developments. Let me give you just three examples:

- When in the mid-1990ies the BSE crisis broke out it shook the CAP to its very core. One of the consequences that were drawn at that time in the Commission was to functionally separate the responsibilities for veterinary and plant health matters from the Directorate-General for Agriculture, and to allocate them to a new dedicated Directorate-General (now DG SANTE). One can assume this was a reasonable decision in order to avoid conflicts of interests or more precisely clashes of political priorities in the same Department. At the same time, however, it generated additional needs for coordination and contributed to institutionally removing agri-relevant aspects from agricultural policy making. Let me just remind you of the regulatory issues linked with the processing of agricultural products, the fight against animal and plant diseases and the use of plant protection products. Subsequently, the Treaty of Amsterdam incorporated this functional change into primary law. For it created, "by way of derogation from Article 37" – the then CAP legal basis - a specific legal basis for "measures in the veterinary and phytosanitary fields which have as their direct objective the protection of public health". In the meantime, Article 168(4)(b) TFEU does no longer

⁷ See *Niemi, Väre* (eds.), *Agriculture and food sector in Finland 2018*, Natural resources and bioeconomy studies 35/2018.

⁸ *McMahon*, *EU Agricultural Law*, 2007, No 2.94 et seq. ; *Mögele*, *Die Reform der Gemeinsamen Agrarpolitik 2013 - Rechtliche und politische Aspekte*, in *Norer/Holzer* (ed.), *Agrarrecht Jahrbuch 2014*, pp. 123, 124 et seq.

carry such a reference to the CAP. It is also telling in that context, that President-elect von der Leyen has mandated the Commissioner-designate responsible for Health to develop the new “Farm to Fork” strategy, not the Commissioner-designate responsible for the CAP.

- Another aspect is linked with the Treaty clause specifying the CAP objectives, i.e. Article 39 TFEU. Amazingly, this provision basically reads the same as in 1958, i.e. it has never been updated even though the world has profoundly changed since. You are aware that the Court of Justice has endowed the CAP legislator with a great deal of discretion as to the application of Article 39 TFEU, which ensures a sufficient degree of regulatory flexibility.⁹ However, over time, the Treaty has been supplemented by a whole series of horizontal clauses, which must also be taken into account in the context of the CAP. This means that the CAP should also pay attention to other legitimate concerns, such as environmental protection,¹⁰ consumer protection,¹¹ animal welfare¹² etc. In the same vein, a series of legal bases were added to the Treaty empowering the legislator in areas other than the CAP to adopt legal acts which, however, can have a significant impact on agriculture. Both developments are legitimate and correspond to the well-known interdependencies between policy areas. For the CAP, however, they lead to a twofold challenge: it should both actively involve the interests of other sectors (e.g. environment, animal welfare, development policy) in the design of its mechanisms and take into account the consequences of agri-relevant regulations in those other areas. And all that on top of the genuine agricultural topics which are the policy’s “raison d’être”. This is a demanding policy profile that has not made designing the CAP any easier, as the ongoing reform discussions are demonstrating, and which may lead to the valid concern, the policy might sometimes simply be overburdened by too many ambitions.
- My third point is of an institutional nature. As one of the last remnants from the “old days”, the Lisbon Treaty upgraded in 2009 the CAP legislative procedure to co-decision between European Parliament and Council, or as the Treaty calls it: “ordinary legislative procedure”.¹³ As a consequence, the European Parliament now acts on an equal footing with the Council in terms of agricultural law-making. This means, in particular, that no legislation can be passed without the Parliament agreeing.

Let us take a look at the practical consequences of that change as they have emerged so far¹⁴:

- First of all, we can see that the Commission's influence on the process has shifted. Whereas in the consultation procedure the actual negotiations took place between Council and Commission, in the ordinary legislative procedure, the Council focuses first on establishing its own line of negotiation with the European Parliament. While here the Commission can contribute its technical expertise, it is less heard when it comes to policy-issues. The Commission’s influence now unfolds mainly in the so-called “trilogue phase” where Parliament, Council and Commission are at the negotiating table. Ideally, the Commission will do three things here: First, it will endeavour to maintain the coherence of the package in order to

⁹ *McMahon*, EU Agricultural Law, 2007, No 1.41.

¹⁰ Article 11 TFEU

¹¹ Article 12 TFEU.

¹² Article 13 TFEU.

¹³ Article 43(2) TFEU in conjunction with Articles 289(1) and 294 TFEU.

¹⁴ See *Mögele*, Die Reform der Gemeinsamen Agrarpolitik 2013 - Rechtliche und politische Aspekte, in No-rer/Holzer (ed.), *Agrarrecht Jahrbuch 2014*, pp. 123, 128 et seq.

avoid losing essential points of its proposal in the final compromise. Second, it will contribute its technical expertise, without which appropriate solutions at European level often cannot be developed. And, as a third point, it will play the role of "facilitator", trying to approximate the positions of the two co-legislators, drafting compromise solutions, or breaking up seemingly unbridgeable differences through the presentation of alternative options. At any rate, at first reading, which is the standard case in agricultural legislation processes, in order to allow the Council to adopt the compromise negotiated with Parliament, Commission approval is required, except where the Council manages to decide with unanimity¹⁵ – which is not often the case.

- On the Council's side, the Presidency, currently held by Finland, has a crucial role to play. Its first task is to forge among Member States consensus or at least a qualified majority on the Council position. This position should ideally contain sufficiently realistic lines of negotiation on the basis of which reaching agreement with the European Parliament is not impossible from the outset. In the trilogues, the Presidency must resolutely represent the mandate it has received. On the other hand, it should muster enough courage and creativity to develop compromise solutions that are acceptable to the Council, without necessarily asking for advance Council approval in each and every individual case.
- In the European Parliament, CAP proposals are traditionally dealt with by the AGRI Committee. It produces a draft parliamentary resolution with amendments to the proposal, which is ultimately put to the vote in a plenary session. Whilst other committees' contributions merely consist in non-binding opinions, there has recently been an interesting development in the context of the CAP revision for the time after 2020. Since one of these proposals (the strategic plan regulation) contains significant environmental and climate-relevant components the ENVI Committee¹⁶ has obtained the status of an associated committee under section 54 of the EP's internal rules.¹⁷ This gives it additional rights of participation and is likely to lead, for the first time, to a stronger institutional integration of environmental and climate aspects into Parliament's decision making on agricultural matters. Discussions between the two committees are ongoing with a view to integrating the ENVI points into the COMAGRI draft report before it is forwarded to plenary.
- In the European Parliament, the rapporteurs have a central role to play. They are crucially involved in the conduct of the negotiations. They have to follow the parliamentary mandate as a whole, keep an eye on the essential interests of their own political group while, at the same time, allowing compromises with the shadow rapporteurs and other key actors, such as the political coordinators of the political groups. This way of working reflects the fact that, unlike most national parliaments, the European Parliament is not organized along the dividing line between majority and opposition, but develops political positions that are independent of Council and Commission.

¹⁵ Article 293 in conjunction with Article 294(3) TFEU.

¹⁶ Committee on Environment, Public Health and Food Safety.

¹⁷ <http://www.europarl.europa.eu/sides/getDoc.do?pubRef=-//EP//TEXT+RULES-EP+20180731+RULE-054+DOC+XML+V0//EN&language=EN&navigationBar=YES> .

4.

After looking into various legal, institutional and policy issues characterising the CAP's development since Finland's accession, let me turn now to the ongoing discussions on the CAP post 2020. This reform process is about the future development of European agriculture with a strong focus on climate and environment, the fairer distribution of income support among Member States and farmers and the strengthening of rural areas. However, as you may know, the Commission has also proposed a new delivery model for the CAP as such.¹⁸ What is this new model about and which legal and institutional issues does it raise?

At the moment, the rules governing the CAP are laid down in great detail at EU level, rules that are subsequently applied by the Member States. This rule-based approach is a key reason for the complexity of the policy and for the fact that its implementation is largely revolving around its legally correct application rather than the delivery of the intended policy goals.

In order to change that, the Commission proposed¹⁹

on the one hand to concentrate, at EU level, on setting out

- the objectives of the CAP,
- the types of measures that can be used and
- a limited number of governance systems (such as IACS) and of basic EU requirements.

On the other hand, it would be up to the Member States

- to break the EU level objectives down into quantified national targets,
- to identify and specify the interventions that are relevant on their territory, and
- to define the legal framework for beneficiaries.

In doing all that Member States would go through several steps of strategic planning: They would

- carry out SWOT²⁰ and needs analyses,
- assemble "their" toolbox by choosing from the types of interventions provided for in EU law (Strategic Plan Regulation) and
- ensure that their choices and their CAP implementation systems are in line with the basic requirements set out in EU law.

In order to ensure the CAP to remain a common policy and to avoid distortions of competition as much as possible, Member States would also have to proceed in the framework of a structured planning process involving a dialogue with stakeholders and civil society. To ensure the increased environmental and climate ambition of the reform to materialise, Member States would be required to demonstrate in the planning process, on the basis of available information, how they intend to realise

¹⁸ See *Mögele*, The Integration of Environmental and Climate Protection into the Common Agricultural Policy – Legal Concepts and Developments, EurUP 2018, pp. 405, 418.

¹⁹ As to the Strategic Plan Regulation see *McMahon*, EU Agricultural Law and Policy, 2019, pp. 227 et seq.

²⁰ Strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats.

the greater overall contribution to the achievement of the specific environmental- and climate-related objectives (“no-backsliding”).²¹

Before being put in operation, Member States’ Draft National Strategic Plans would, at the end of the process, be subject to Commission scrutiny and approval.²² This is meant to create greater “policy discipline” in comparison with the status quo where Member States can autonomously decide on the options they wish to implement.

I could now extensively dwell on the proposed model and its various components. I prefer, however, to concentrate on one specific point which, in my view, truly represents a legal innovation. Under the proposed model the EU will no longer set detailed rules for individual beneficiaries, but it will establish fewer EU rules and requirements which are only addressed to the Member States. The Member States would in turn establish on that basis, by means of national law, the legal framework actually applicable to farmers. The Commission would thus concentrate in the future on its relations with Member States, and leave it to them to design the rules applicable at farm level.

The reasons underpinning that construction are basically twofold:

- First, there is the issue of simplification. The CAP has over time become more and more complex, and administratively burdensome for farmers and national administrations. Member States have been in the past keen to ensure in their CAP implementation maximum legal certainty, in particular, to avoid financial corrections. In case of doubt, they tend to apply the most stringent option towards their farmers. This has created a dynamic, which resulted in producing more and more rules and controls and it has triggered requests for more and more interpretations and guidelines. Reversing that trend and simplifying the policy can, from an EU perspective, only work by reducing and limiting the number, scope and depth of the rules adopted at EU level, i.e. by Parliament and Council and by the Commission. A CAP with a lighter EU framework that leaves greater margins to Member States on the ground is quite likely to have good potential to simplify the lives of farmers.
- Second, for a performance-based CAP, as proposed by the Commission, the focus is on what the policy should achieve and whether it achieves its goals, instead of concentrating in great detail on how this is done. Given the workload linked with introducing the performance orientation, it is also clear, that a performance approach cannot simply be added to the current compliance-based CAP delivery model. An accumulation of both layers would undoubtedly overstretch the administrative capacity of farmers, Member States and Commission. That is why the new model would work with less EU rules and shift the current focus of the EU audit and assurance mechanism from legality and regularity of individual transactions to Member States’ performance in reaching objectives, or more precisely, in reaching the targets they have set in their own strategic plans. This new approach would of course also be reflected in the Commission’s audit approach.

²¹ Article 92 Strategic Plan Regulation (Commission proposal).

²² Article 106 Strategic Plan Regulation (Commission proposal).

5.

There is of course still another overriding theme of the CAP post 2020 discussions, and that is “subsidiarity”. This is about responding to the considerable diversity and heterogeneity of agriculture in an EU of 28 Member States, reaching from Lapland to Sicily and from the Ukrainian border to the Atlantic coast.

The fact that one size does not fit all had already left its traces in the results of the CAP reform in 2013. This reform opened up a large degree of flexibility by offering a multitude of alternative implementation options that Member States and regions have actually used in practice. It is very unlikely for this trend to stop this time or even to revert. That is why the proposals give Member States a considerable role in designing “their policy mix”. If done well, giving Member States appropriate discretion can in my view help turning the CAP into a policy that is better targeted at the specific problems and needs on the ground. I have already explained how that process would be framed by EU requirements, a (hopefully) rational and structured planning process and – something that does currently not exist in this form - Commission scrutiny and approval at the end.

However, this aspect in the proposals has repeatedly triggered the concern, the new delivery model would ultimately lead to a renationalisation of the CAP. Against this background, the question of the “C” in the CAP arises: Does the CAP proposed by the Commission still deserve to be qualified as “common”? This question has, in particular, been raised in the agricultural committee of the European Parliament and by farmers’ organizations. I would like to refrain at this point from discussing that question from a policy perspective and rather try to deal with it in a legal context. What are the legal parameters in the Treaty that should be examined, and are there elements in the Court’s case law casting light on the issue?

First of all, it is clear from the TFEU that the creation of a common agricultural policy is one of the Union’s tasks. However, when it comes to the means or forms of organization to be used, the Treaty leaves wide scope for the EU legislator. The definition of common competition rules is a possible option as are the coordination of national market organizations or the creation of a European market organization. What matters most is, that the agricultural policy objectives set out in Article 39 TFEU are pursued. As stated in Article 40(2) TFEU, all necessary measures and instruments may be used for this purpose. It should also be borne in mind that, since the Treaty of Lisbon, the TFEU clarifies that the Common Agricultural Policy is not, as has been formerly advocated, an exclusive, but rather a shared EU competence.²³ Thus, the principle of subsidiarity²⁴ applies, the main purpose of which is to curb the EU’s “regulatory ambition” if the objectives in question can be achieved at least as well at national or regional level. Leaving room for maneuver for the national legislator can well be interpreted as a possible way to apply the principle of subsidiarity in the CAP context.

Moreover, the TFEU itself assumes that the content of the common agricultural policy must take account of the diversity of European agriculture. According to Article 39(2) TFEU, “the specific nature of agricultural activity, which derives from the social structure of agriculture and from structural and

²³ Article 4(2)(d) TFEU.

²⁴ Article 5(3) TEU.

natural disparities between the various agricultural regions”, must be taken into account when designing the CAP. The Court of Justice has already explicitly pointed out the importance of this provision in its case-law.

All this demonstrates, in my view, that European agricultural policy cannot only be regarded as "common" if it subjects its support instruments to uniform criteria that apply to all parties concerned across the EU. The treaty rather grants the EU legislator a wide scope of discretion within which the agricultural policy objectives can be pursued in a differentiated manner and in accordance with the respective national and regional needs. As the ECJ has consistently emphasized, this discretion reflects the political responsibility conferred on the legislator by the Treaty, which can only be judicially reviewed to ensure that the measures taken do not involve a manifest error or misuse of powers.²⁵

In addition, the prohibition of discrimination in the framework of the CAP, which is merely an agricultural expression of the general principle, should not be lost sight of in this context. Accordingly, "comparable situations should not be treated differently and different situations not treated alike unless such treatment is objectively justified".²⁶ However, the Court of Justice delimits from this test those types of cases in which the legislator gives Member States a certain discretion for the purpose of making CAP payments. The ECJ puts the granting of such discretion in the context of the Common Agricultural Policy as an area of shared competence and thus of the application of the subsidiarity principle. In other words, Member States may take measures which differ from each other in their procedural and substantive conditions, without the resulting differences being treated as discrimination.²⁷ According to that case-law, the ECJ rejected e.g. a discriminatory nature of Article 69 of Regulation (EC) No 1782/2003. The national and regional discretionary margins provided for in the direct payment scheme adopted in 2013 may therefore legally also be considered to be free of discrimination. This approach should in any event apply beyond the cases at hand, provided that the difference in treatment is sufficiently limited by formal and material criteria and based on appropriate objective considerations.²⁸ Against this background, I tend to conclude that the new delivery model proposed by the Commission is well capable of surviving a legal review on the basis of the criteria set out above.

6.

The Commission tabled its proposals for the CAP post 2020 in June 2018.²⁹ Despite a multitude of meetings, discussions and explanatory papers neither Parliament nor Council have managed so far to define their negotiation positions, let alone to start negotiating. This is certainly a headache for the Finish Presidency, which will soon issue another progress report, but also for farmers. The reasons for the delay seem to be pretty obvious. First, the parliamentary elections in May slowed down the process. Now the transition from the outgoing to the incoming new Commission will only take place on 1 December, which does not help either. The biggest stumbling block, however, is the fact that the

²⁵ ECJ C-373/11 Pannelinios Syndesmos, No 40.

²⁶ ECJ, C-545/11 Agrargenossenschaft Neuzelle e.G, No 42; C-373/11 Panellinios Syndemos, No 22.

²⁷ ECJ, C-373/11 Panellinios Syndemos, No 23; C-1101/12 Schaible, No 87.

²⁸ ECJ, C-313/04 Egenberger, No 51 et seq.

²⁹ Proposal for a Strategic Plan Regulation (SPR), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2018%3A392%3AFIN>; Proposal for a Horizontal Regulation (HZR) https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:6cb59a1e-6580-11e8-ab9c-01aa75ed71a1.0003.03/DOC_1&format=PDF.

Heads of State and Government have still not made up their minds as to the MFF 2021-2027. This is in a way due to the BREXIT limbo but, in my view, more prominently to the fact that decisions of such an order of magnitude are usually not taken more than a year ahead of the final deadline. And, as long as the size of the allocation for the CAP remains open neither Parliament nor Council are likely to feel much pressure to rush into CAP trilogues. It is difficult to reach a decision on CAP reform, before the decision on the MFF has been taken. This situation should remind us of 2013 when the MFF agreement in the European Council was reached in February which led Parliament and Council to wrapping up their positions so that CAP trilogues could start in April and be concluded by the end of June.³⁰ Now, whether this timing may be seen as a blueprint for 2020 – nobody knows. But as time is running there is a growing need for transitional arrangements that should be in place ahead of 2021 to avoid the financial parts of the CAP to come to a halt. That's why the Commission has just submitted proposals for transitional arrangements by which the existing policy would be extended by one year, following the principle "new money for old measures". This may sound technical but it would not be surprising should the discussions on the transition not become very interesting, both politically and legally.

³⁰ *Mögele*, Die Reform der Gemeinsamen Agrarpolitik 2013 - Rechtliche und politische Aspekte, in Norer/Holzer (ed.), *Agrarrecht Jahrbuch 2014*, pp. 123, 128 et seq.